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Neuropharmacological links Between Diabetes and Alzheimer's Disease: Molecular crosstalk and Therapeutic Potential of Flavonoids

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ABSTRACT

Objectives: To analyze the molecular and neuropharmacological links between Diabetes and Alzheimer's Disease and to evaluate the therapeutic potential of flavonoids in diabetes-associated Alzheimer's disease (DAAD).

Material and Method: Using indexed biomedical literature, a narrative evaluation of experimental, preclinical, and clinical studies addressing insulin resistance, oxidative stress, neuroinflammation, amyloid pathology, and flavonoid-mediated neuroprotection in DM and AD was carried out.

Result: DM and AD share comparable pathophysiological pathways including insulin resistance, mitochondrial dysfunction, oxidative stress, chronic inflammation, advanced glycation end products (AGEs), and decreased SIRT1/AMPK signalling. Brain insulin resistance relates to amyloid- β build up and tau hyperphosphorylation. In experimental models, flavonoids including quercetin, rutin, kaempferol, genistein, luteolin, naringenin, and hesperidin demonstrate insulin-sensitizing, anti-inflammatory, anti-amyloidogenic, and anticholinesterase properties.

Conclusion: Flavonoids are prospective multi-target therapeutic agents for DAAD, as they modulate shared molecular pathways of DM and AD. Nevertheless, in order to verify the efficacy, safety, and optimal administration strategies, well-designed clinical trials are necessary.

Keywords: Flavonoids, Diabetes mellitus(DM), Alzheimer's disease(AD), Diabetes-associated Alzheimer's Disease (DAAD), Acetylcholine

INTRODUCTION

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a specific form of dementia has been significant linked to Type 2 diabetes (T2DM). It is estimated that 1 in 15 adults over the age of 65 are impacted by Alzheimer's. The AD is International Organization estimated approx. 69 million individuals worldwide suffered from dementia in 2025 according to these numbers' prediction indicate that number will triple by 2050. Early symptoms of the Alzheimer's disease include confusion, difficulty in talking, tongue tingling, and amnesia, all stemming from damage to brain cells and neurons. The correlation between AD and DM is apparent, especially as individuals over the age of 60 with T2DM (Type 2 diabetes Meletus) are thought to be twice as likely to acquire Alzheimer's as people without diabetes[1]. Diabetes can impair the Sensitive blood vessels that supply cells and neurons, that is possibilities prevalence of AD is higher among diabetic individuals, leading to potential harm to the neurons and cells. Consequently, such damage to brain cells could be an aspect in the development of AD [2].

Some individuals use the term "Type 3 diabetes" to describe the symptoms of Alzheimer's, presenting that diabetes type 3 affects the brain and leads to Alzheimer's disease, this terminology is not officially recognized by world health organizations and the majority of medical professionals don't use it for diagnosis. The concept of Type 3 diabetes was introduced by certain scientists who hypothesized that brain insulin dysregulation cause dementia . According to this viewpoint Alzheimer's disease is categorized as a neuroendocrine breakdown affecting insulin and signalling between insulin and insulin-like growth factor (IGF), accompanied by reactive oxidative damage and inflammation. In spite of this a review from trusted source in 2008 underscores that Alzheimer's disease primarily impact on brain, and the designation of "Type 3 diabetes"

appropriately reflects this aspect of the condition.

Numerous investigations have demonstrated the link between diabetes and cognitive deterioration. One study found that Type 1 diabetics had approx. 95% higher risk of developing dementia [3]. Individuals with Type 1 diabetes are more susceptible to dementia compared to those people without diabetes. And research also indicates that beta-amyloid protein, a key protein associated with Alzheimer's disease, significantly increases in individuals with high level of blood sugar, including those with Type 2 diabetes [4]. People with Type 2 diabetes experience faster cognitive deterioration, especially in executive function and information processing speed, and early-stage diabetics may display indications of brain damage. Furthermore, Research has indicated that people with Type 2 diabetes are more likely to develop Alzheimer's disease as they age [5] .

PATHOPHYSIOLOGY OF DIABETES-ASSOCIATED ALZHEIMER'S DISEASE

Pathways Involved in Diabetes:

DM manifests as a metabolic condition that is symbolized by the inability of insulin hormone secretion or function. Insulin, produced by pancreatic β -cells, facilitates glucose absorption by cells for energy requirements [6]. When insulin is deficient or functions abnormally, cells fail to absorb glucose, leading to hyperglycemia [7] . In healthy individuals, blood glucose levels are tightly regulated, with post-meal plasma glucose rising modestly and fasting plasma glucose remaining within specific ranges [8] . However, during the development of diabetes mellitus, blood glucose regulation deviates from the norm, with insulin resistance preceding the onset of the disease. Hyperglycemia also diminishes communication between Silent information regulator and 5-Adenosine

monophosphate-activated protein kinase (AMPK), known as sirtuin 1 (SIRT1), crucial for cellular functions [9]. SIRT1, a key regulator of energy metabolism, modulates glucose production, lipid metabolism, insulin synthesis, and sensitivity, as well as the activity of mitochondrial biogenesis regulators and peroxisome proliferator-activated receptors [10].

Pathways involved in Alzheimer's:

AD is the neurodegenerative disease that is most common among the elderly, characterized by memory impairment and deficits in language, spatial skills, problem-solving, and socio-affective behavior [11]. Neurofibrillary tangles (NFTs) containing hyperphosphorylated tau proteins and insoluble β -amyloid peptides form plaques, contributing to the disease's pathogenesis [12]. SIRT1 down-regulation in the parietal cortex of AD patients is associated with disease progression, while studies suggest that SIRT1 activation may mitigate β -amyloid peptide production [13],[14]. Additionally, β -amyloid plaques induce glial cell Ca^{2+} channel changes, that lead to reactive oxygen species (ROS) generation and oxidative stress [15].

Common Pathways Involved in Diabetes-associated Alzheimer's Disease:

The convergence of DM and AD is of elevated interest to health officials due to shared risk factors and pathological processes, including inflammation, oxidative stress, altered energy homeostasis, and aging-related epigenetic changes [16],[17]. SIRT1 down-regulation, evident in both AD and DM models, contributes to metabolic and neurodegenerative pathology [18].

Moreover, insulin resistance or deficiency in DM leads to reduced acetyl-coenzyme A synthesis, exacerbating neuronal cell death [19]. Inflammation, characterized by elevated interleukin 6 (IL-6) levels in Type 2 diabetes and the presence of inflammatory markers in AD, further underscores the shared pathophysiology between the two conditions [20],[21]. Dysregulated insulin signaling elevates ROS production that promotes mitochondrial dysfunction and apoptosis [22]. The outcomes oxidative stress triggers pro-inflammatory cytokine release and occur β -amyloid peptide formation that exacerbates neurotoxicity. SIRT1 down-regulation further intensifies neurotoxicity by activating the NF- κ B signaling pathway [23].

Therefore, the fact is evident that diabetes mellitus (DM) increases the risk of Alzheimer's disease the reverse it. A reasonable justification lies in the β -amyloid peptide developed in AD patients, which disrupts insulin receptor autophosphorylation, that consequently prevents insulin binding to its receptor and causing insulin resistance. Given the mechanisms and opposite impact between DM and AD, it is increased awareness that both pathologies are interconnected [24]. This relative connection emphasizes the complexity of Diabetes-associated Alzheimer's Disease and lightens the importance of understanding connected pathways and major risk factors underlying both diseases. Such insights are crucial for the growth of effective treatment approaches that target common pathological mechanisms and deal with the multifaceted nature of this complex junction of diseases. Pathogenesis of Diabetes-associated Alzheimer's Disease is shown in Figure 1.

Fig.1:-Pathogenesis of Diabetes-associated Alzheimer's Disease

Oxidative damage occurs when the body's natural antioxidant defenses fail to balance the production of reactive oxygen species. Hyperglycemia-mediated oxidative damage is considered a principal factor contributing to the growth of Diabetes-associated Alzheimer's Disease [25]. Both types of diabetes mellitus exhibit elevated ROS generation due to hyperglycemia [26],[27]. In Diabetes-associated Alzheimer's Disease, high ROS levels lead to oxidative damage and downregulation of natural antioxidant defenses [28],[29]. Over time, elevated ROS levels induce apoptosis in the brain by directly damaging proteins, lipids, and DNA[30]. Numerous studies have demonstrated that oxidative damage exacerbates the aberrant progression of Alzheimer's disease in diabetes mellitus, potentially leading to morphological and physiological complications [31]. AGEs, or advanced glycation end products, build up in a variety of tissues during normal aging and accelerate in

diabetes mellitus [32]. The way that AGEs and their receptors (RAGE) interact influences the pathophysiology of diabetes as well as neurodegenerative illnesses like Alzheimer's [30]. In vitro glycation of Aβ promotes its aggregation, while τ glycation promotes PHF formation [33]. AGEs are generated from carbonyl compounds produced during sugar auto-oxidation and other metabolic pathways [34]. Human serum contains AGEs AGE-1 and AGE-2, found in higher concentrations in individuals with both type 1 and type 2 diabetes [35]. AGEs receptors, including RAGE and others, mediate several negative reactions of glycations, contributing to aging disorders and diabetic complications [36],[35]

TREATMENT STRATEGIES FOR DIABETES-ASSOCIATED ALZHEIMER'S DISEASE

Lifestyle Intervention

Lifestyle modifications, including physical activity and nutritional counseling, are

among the first interventions recommended for patients with diabetes and insulin resistance. These interventions have shown benefits in reducing the incidence of diabetes and cognitive decline [37],[38]. Diets rich in antioxidants and low on the glycemic index have demonstrated improvements in insulin sensitivity and AD molecular markers [39],[40]. Lifestyle modifications should be incorporated into non-pharmacological treatment plans and preventative measures for patients with diabetes, insulin resistance, and AD.

Pharmacological Treatment

Several pharmacological interventions are available for the management of Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) and Alzheimer's disease (AD). Insulin therapy administered systematically has been associated with improvements in cognition and reductions in pathological amyloid beta accumulation [41],[42].

Oral Hypoglycemic Drugs

Sulfonylureas: Clinical data suggests that certain oral hypoglycemic agents (OHAs) are linked to a lower risk of dementia [43]. Sulfonylureas may regulate the oxidative damage associated with diabetes[44]. But more investigation is required to confirm their effectiveness as potential therapeutic options for AD. Sulfonylureas, like insulin therapy, can also cause severe hypoglycemic episodes [45].

Metformin: Metformin has shown controversial results in treating AD. It may lessen the activation of phosphokinases and block mitochondrial respiratory chain complex 1, potentially improving AD pathology [46],[47],[48].

Thiazolidinediones (TZDs): TZDs, such as pioglitazone, have been studied for their potential to reduce amyloid beta plaque formation and enhance cognition and memory in early Alzheimer's disease stages [49].

- **DPP4 inhibitors:** DPP4 inhibitors, like vildagliptin and sitagliptin, have been associated with improvements in memory retention, tau phosphorylation, and a reduction of beta-amyloid accumulation [50].

GLP-1RAs (Glucagon-like Peptide-1 Receptor Agonists): GLP-1 and GIP analogs possess neuroprotective properties in the CNS. Studies have shown that GLP-1 agonists may reduce glucose metabolism decline in AD patients [51].

Novel Medications: Azeliragon, a novel medication, has demonstrated the ability to reduce brain inflammation and amyloid deposition in AD patients. Further clinical trials are needed to validate its therapeutic efficacy[52],[53].

Flavonoids

Flavonoids are also known as phytochemicals derived from plants exert a range of biological activities by regulating multiple cellular molecular pathways Which makes them worthwhile for human health [54]. Which makes them worthwhile. Which makes them worthwhile several phytonutrients, flavanones, as highlighted by Teng et al. (2019), exhibit the highest bioavailability among flavonoid compounds. Flavonoids are essential nutritive values known for their preventive and therapeutic effects against Alzheimer's disease and Type 2 diabetes mellitus [55].

These compounds mostly found in fruits and vegetables have got attention for their potential role in mitigating the risk and progression of Alzheimer's and T2DM. Through their antioxidative and anti-inflammatory properties, flavonoids Participate to cellular protection and metabolic regulation providing opportunities for growth for disease prevention and management (Figure 2).

Fig.2:-Role of Flavonoids in prevention of Diabetes and Alzheimer's disease

The six different flavonoid subclasses include anthocyanidins, flavanols, flavones, flavanones, and isoflavones[56]. These compounds given consideration to plant as secondary metabolites, possess various physiological activities like antiviral, anti-allergic, antibacterial, and anti-inflammatory properties and also contributing to the color and fragrance of flowers [57].

Flavonoids display the capacity to modulate hepatic enzyme activities, lipid profiles, and glucose metabolism, potentially impacting the beginning of

T2DM and Alzheimer's disease with their associated complications [57]. The structure of a flavonoid, illustrated in Figure 3, follows a C6C3C6 configuration contain of a heterocyclic oxygenated benzopyran ring and two aromatic rings. This unique structure is the foundation of their diverse biological activities and potential therapeutic effects in various health activity. Figure 3 shows the chemical structure of a flavonoid Hispidone.

Fig.3:-Chemical structure of Flavonoid (Hispidone- PubChem CID -9997719)

Role of Flavonoids in Diabetes

Flavonoids have been reported to exert numerous beneficial health effects on metabolic diseases, including diabetes [58]. Their antidiabetic action involves the regulation of glucose uptake, insulin secretion, insulin signaling, carbohydrate digestion, and adipose disposition [59]. Flavonoids target different molecules that regulate these activities, including enhance β -cell proliferation, stimulating insulin secretion, decreased apoptosis, and ameliorating hyperglycemia by regulating hepatic glucose metabolism [60],[61].

Anthocyanins found abundantly in pears, apples, and blueberries, represent high

sources of anthocyanins known to reduce the danger of type 2 diabetes [62],[63] This was validated by a US-based study involving 200,000 men and women, which evaluated the association between flavonoid subclass consumption and diabetes risk (64). The hydroxyl group, α , and β ketones of flavonoids are believed to account for the majority of their bioactivity (Table- 1).

Flavonoids emerge as promising natural compounds for mitigating diabetes risk and improving metabolic health through their multifaceted mechanisms of action, highlighting their potential as therapeutic agents in diabetes management [65].

Table 1:-Aspects of Flavonoids in the control of Diabetes Mellitus

S. No.	Flavonoids	Mechanism of Action	Reference
1.	Hesperidin	Blood glucose by modifying the function of enzymes that regulate glucose	Akiyama et al., 2010
2.	Naringenin	High blood sugar levels and \uparrow SOD, an antioxidant enzyme.	Hassanein et al., 2014
3.	Apigenin	Apoptosis, \uparrow antioxidant, and mitochondrial protection.	Suh et al., 2012
4.	Baicalein	Enhanced islet β -cell mass and survival as well as improved glucose tolerance.	Fu et al., 2014
5.	Luteolin	Elevated antioxidants and HO-1 expression.	Wang et al., 2011

Flavonoids with Anti-Diabetic Properties:

Flavanol: Flavanols are distinguished by an unsaturated carbon ring at carbons 2-4, hydroxylated at carbon 3, and oxidized at carbon 4. They are mostly found in berries, kale, grapes and lettuce etc. [66]

Flavanones: It Also known as di-hydro flavones, flavanones is a saturated, oxidized carbon ring. Citrus fruits are mostly rich in flavanones, which exhibit potential effect of antioxidant properties and free radical scavenging abilities[67],[68].

Flavones: Flavones have a ketone group at carbon 4 and an unsaturated carbon ring at carbons 2-3, but they do not have hydroxylation at carbon 3. Different fruits, leaves, and flowers synthesize them [63]

Isoflavones: Isoflavones like genistein and daidzein, which are mostly found in soybeans, legumes, and some microorganisms, have been demonstrated to boost insulin release by pancreatic beta cells, helping to prevent diabetes [69].

Anthocyanins: Fruits and flowers are abundant in anthocyanins, which are hydrophilic and unsaturated flavonoids.

They are ingested in large quantities through diet, and research on animals and cell lines has suggested that they may have anti-diabetic effects [69]

Aspects of Flavonoids in Alzheimer's Disease:

Flavonoids as Neuroprotective Agents: These compounds are useful in the fight against neurodegenerative illnesses because they improve cognitive function and have neuroprotective qualities against neuroinflammation [70], for example, recent research has shown that icariin, a flavonoid derived from the Chinese herb Epimedium brevicornis, has neuroprotective properties[71].

Baicalein is obtained from Scutellarin baicalinase's, appears significant neuroprotective potential, ameliorating memory deficits and synaptic plasticity in Alzheimer's Disease mouse models [72]. In addition, certain flavonoids have been evaluated for their anticholinesterase activity, which help to prevent neuronal damage in the hippocampus region especially relevant in Alzheimer's disease pathology [73]

Table 2:-Aspects of Flavonoids in the Management of Alzheimer's Disease

S. No.	Flavonoid	Mechanism of Action	References
1.	Hesperidin	Supports nervous variation and diminish β amyloid plaques and blocks the AChE	Panche et al., 2016
2.	Anthocyanin	Diminish the β amyloid protein	Vepsalane et al., 2013
3.	Naringenin	Blocks the neuronal death	Hernandez-Mantes et al., 2006
4.	Quercetin	Blocks the cell death and enhances AMPK role of downregulation of tau phosphorylation	Lee et al., 2003
5.	Luteolin	Diminish $A\beta$ plaque formation	Rezai-zadeh et al., 2009
6.	Genistein	Enhances neural survival	Weinreb et al., 2009
7.	Myricetin	Blocks the butyl cholinesterase activity	Leclerc et al., 2001

Cholinesterase Inhibition through

Flavonoids: Acetylcholine (ACh) is an essential neurotransmitter involved in impulse transmission within various neurotransmitters [74]. Acetylcholinesterase (AChE) and butyrylcholinesterase (BChE) are major cholinesterase enzymes responsible for degrading ACh, crucial for neurotransmission between synapses [75], [76]. Research indicates lower ACh levels in Alzheimer's disease brains and cholinesterase inhibitors elevate Acetylcholine esterase levels, facilitating impulse transmission at synaptic junctions. Uriarte-Pueyo and Calvo identified 128 flavonoids with Acetyl choline esterase-blocking action that suggesting flavonoids as potential anti-Alzheimer agents [71]. Quercetin has shown high efficacy as an AChE blocker among various flavonoids [77]. Due to their potency as AChE blockers, flavonoids are considered promising candidates for developing innovative anti-Alzheimer medications [78].

Flavonoids as Cognition Enhancers:

Research suggests suggesting flavonoids could postpone Alzheimer's and reverse cognitive deficits, indicating therapeutic

potential [79]. Combining the consumption of flavonoid-rich fruits with quercetin administration enhances mental capacity, memory retention, and recuperation from both temporary and long-term memory loss. Several studies have highlighted Flavonoids' positive impact on learning and memory [80]. Anthocyanin-rich mulberry extract corrected reduced cognitive function in mice with AD-like neurodegeneration and accelerated senescence. Although research on cognition and mental retention in animal models fed with diets high in flavonoids is limited, dietary flavonoids have been shown to enhance cognitive function and positively impact AD pathophysiology in meta-analyses. Anthocyanin-enriched wheat grain diets or extracts have also improved mental abilities in mouse models of AD in recent studies [81],[82]

Aspects of Flavonoids in Diabetes-Associated AD:

Flavonoids play a therapeutic role in Alzheimer's and diabetes, particularly in the treatment of Alzheimer's disease associated with diabetes. Table 3 outlines key flavonoids used in Diabetes-associated Alzheimer's Disease.

Table 3:-Common Flavonoids in Diabetes-associated Alzheimer's Disease

S. No.	Flavonoids	Mechanism of action	Reference
1.	Quercetin	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Suppress apoptosis enhances the AMPK action of downregulation of tau phosphorylation enhanced the process by which enzyme that limits the pace of glycogen production is called glycogen synthase. • Blocking both the transcriptional factors along with the action of mTORC1/ p70S6K. • Blocking action of NF-κB and caspase-3 interaction. • Reduced oxidative stress and hyperglycaemia. Alloxan in mice with type 2 diabetes. Alam 2014 uses the mitochondrial pathway and NF-κB 	Lee et al., 2003

		signalling to heal β -cell death.	
2.	Genistein	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enhance neural survival Decrease cell death. \downarrow Glucose, HbA1c, creative protein, TNFα and TGFβ1 protein factors. Decreased hyperglycemia via minimizing islet cell loss. 	Weinreb et al., 2009
3.	Baicalein	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enhanced dopaminergic level Enhanced glucose tolerance, as well as the mass and lifespan of islet β-cells. Inhibition and action of NF-κB, decrease iNOS, TGF-β1, ALP, SGOT and SGPT. Enhancement of insulin resistance, concealed by phosphorylating AMPKα AND INS-1. brought back the disability of PI3K/Akt pathway and \downarrow GSK3β. 	El-Bassossy et al., 2014
4.	Luteolin	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Declined Aβ plaque formation. decreased of the NF-κB pathway Diminishing effect of NF-κB was implemented in decline via luteolin with elevation of iNOS. 	Rezai-zadeh et al., 2009
5.	Naringenin	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Decreasing neuronal death Intestinal α-glucosidase activity is declining. Diabetic rats caused by high HFD-STZ. decreased oxidative damage (Priscilla 2014). Hyperglycemia and \uparrow antioxidant enzyme (SOD). Decline of fasting glucose and inflammatory cytokines. 	Hernandez-Mantes et al., 2006
6.	Hesperidin	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Supports neural differentiation Decline β amyloid plaques Inhibit AChE. Inhibits the production of free radicals and the release of cytokines (IL-1β and TNF-α). Reduces and suppresses the production of free radicals and the release of cytokines (IL-1β and TNF-α). Regulates their glycolysis, gluconeogenesis, and hepatic glycogen stores. 	Mahmoud et al., 2012

The following section explains the significance of several other flavonoids, including quercetin, rutin, kaempferol, etc., in Diabetes-associated AD. Specific methods of treating Alzheimer's disease are not known but these three flavonoids have a well-defined mechanism for treating diabetes [83].

Quercetin: It is the most prevalent flavonoid in human diets, shows promise in treating AD and T2DM [37]. In INS-1 cells, quercetin increased insulin secretion in response to glucose and pre-induced oxidative damage [26]. The biological mechanism of quercetin involves the activation of extracellular signal-regulated kinase (ERK1/2), potentially through the Akt signaling pathway's influence on

SIRT1 activity upregulation, providing therapeutic benefits for type 2 diabetes [25]. Quercetin's role in diabetic peripheral neuropathy may possess neuroprotective qualities, as demonstrated by numerous in vivo and in vitro investigations [37]. By activating AMPK and reducing mitochondrial inhibition, quercetin produces neuroprotective effects [2]. Additional investigation is required to ascertain the most effective way to use bitter melon as a prophylactic measure in medicine and understand quercetin's impacts on AD and T2DM [22]

Kaempferol: It is a non-toxic flavonoid, offers multiple therapeutic benefits for AD and T2DM. Its main antidiabetic effects include AMP-induced cellular protein expression and activation, suppression of caspase-3-mediated cellular death activity, and enhanced β -cell secretion and production of insulin [84]. Additionally, kaempferol promotes cellular glucose uptake through the PI3K and protein kinase C pathways, enhancing the production of glucose transporters [85],[86] Kaempferol also decreases pro-inflammatory signaling mediated by RhoA/Rho-kinase, reducing diabetic kidney disease in cell studies [87]. However more investigation is needed to fully comprehend kaempferol's function in AD[88].

Rutin: Rutin was shown in a recent study to reduced blood sugar levels in mice with insulin resistance by utilizing GLUT4 translocation and increasing Activity of insulin-dependent receptor kinase (IRK) [89]. Rutin also protects diabetes in the following ways: decreasing small intestine absorption of carbohydrates, inhibiting gluconeogenesis, stimulating β -cell insulin secretion, and shielding the Langerhans islets from deteriorating condition [90],[91] Additionally, rutin shows promise as a treatment for AD, mitigating oxidative damage associated with neuronal

cell loss, inhibiting A β aggregation, and reducing inflammatory markers of neurodegeneration [92]

Genistein: The aggregation of A β proteins significantly impacts AD pathophysiology and is the primary target for therapeutic development [93]. Genistein, the primary phytoestrogen found in soybeans, regulates estrogen's pharmacological effects effectively[94]. By functioning as a stimulant on estrogen receptors (ERs), Genistein may prevent neuronal death caused by A β [95] Genistein's protective feature is attributed to its suppression of the opening of the mitochondrial transition pore, preventing reactive oxygen species (ROS) release from mitochondria to PC12 cells caused by β -amyloid peptides 25–35 [96]Genistein has neuroprotective properties and prevents acetylcholine-induced neurotoxicity without proliferative adverse effects on uterine endometrial cells, suggesting its potential as a therapeutic agent in AD management [97]. However, there are few clinical studies on Genistein's use as a therapeutic agent despite reports of its neuroprotective properties.

Luteolin: Alzheimer's disease is the most common neurodegenerative illness leading to senile dementia, with A β plaque formation being a defining feature in its pathology. Luteolin reduced A β generation in primary neuronal cells from Sweep overexpressing mice, indicating its potential to reduce A β [98].Luteolin deactivates the GSK-3 α isoform's catalytic core, p-PS1, enhancing the γ -secretase complex's catalytic core, which may be the mechanism underlying the decrease of A β generation [99],[100]. Recent studies have shown that luteolin can reduce Alzheimer's diseases pathology in mice with traumatic brain injury and in rats with streptozotocin-stimulated Alzheimer's disease, indicating its potential protective

effects on hippocampal organization and cognitive deficits [101],[102]

Hesperidin: A β deposition inhibits neuronal insulin signaling and decreases insulin receptor activity on the membrane in AD patients, resulting in decreased insulin levels and GLUTs in the brain. Hesperidin can somewhat improve A β -impaired glucose intake by inhibiting autophagy. Hesperidin at a dose of 1–20 μ M significantly decreases neuronal autophagy [103], [104], [105]Hesperidin strongly prevents lipid oxidation-induced oxidative damage, an aspect of AD pathophysiology related to A β aggregation, with IC50 values of 179.1 μ M [106].

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

In conclusion, the exploration of flavonoids within the structure of Alzheimer's disease and T2DM underscores their Major potential as therapeutic agents. Flavonoids such as quercetin, rutin, kaempferol, genistein, luteolin, and hesperidin display a variety of attributes that target various aspects of Alzheimer's disease and Type-2 Diabetes mellitus pathogenesis, such as inflammation, oxidative stress, and advanced glycation end products. These substances are effective in improving glucose metabolism, boosting insulin signalling, reducing the production of A β plaque, and having neuroprotective effects. And they're the capacity to navigate the BBB (Blood brain barrier) and modulate cellular and enzymatic processes provides a useful path for innovative treatment approaches. However, challenges like limited bioavailability and potential interactions with pharmaceutical agents enlightened the need for future research into optimal flavonoid utilization as nutraceuticals and therapeutic drugs.

In future continues to investigation into the mechanisms beneath flavonoid-mediated

therapeutic effects is essential. And exploring combination therapies and lifestyle modifications, including dietary interventions rich in flavonoids may offer synergistic benefits in decreasing of risk factors and slow disease progression, and improving clinical results for individuals with Diabetes-associated Alzheimer's Disease. More research is required to clarify the exact molecular pathways involved in flavonoid action and to give their potential synergistic effects when combined. Furthermore, it is necessary to conduct clinical trials to evaluate the safety and efficacy of flavonoid-based therapies across a range of patient populations. A promising approach to tackling the intricate interactions between AD and T2DM pathophysiology is provided by the multifunctional characteristics of flavonoids. We may work toward better management and prevention measures for Alzheimer's disease connected to diabetes by expanding our knowledge and application of flavonoids as therapeutic agents. This will enhance the lives of individuals affected.

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STATEMENTS AND DECLARATIONS

Human and Animal Rights

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Declaration of AI Use

we confirmed that the above given data is not AI generated.

Conflict of Interest

We do not have any conflict of interest.

Ethical Approval

Not applicable

Data Availability Statement

We confirm that the data supporting the findings of this study will be shared upon reasonable request.

Author Contributions

The authors contribute to the study's conception and design only by K.J and wrote the first draft of the manuscript, and prepared Figure and reviewed and edited the manuscript further. And the authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Competing Interests

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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